

SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF YARNS AND THERMOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES IN 3D BRAIDED TUBULAR COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses a method which links analytically the following sequential events: the braiding of a class of 3D tubular preforms to be characterized by selected braiding parameters; the yarn structure topology in the braided preforms to be characterized by the braiding procedure; the final yarn structure in the preforms after matrix-consolidation to be determined by the composites exterior dimensions; and the thermomechanical properties of the composites to be determined by a micromechanics model. These sequential events form a closed design-analysis loop, linking the final composite properties all the way to the braiding details of the preforms.

The 4-step 1x1 braiding procedure is utilized throughout the analytical development; graphite yarns and epoxy resin are used in the illustrative examples. It is demonstrated that use of the developed interrelationships can lead to an optimal design, which begins with the design of the braiding setup all the way to the expected properties of the composites.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, various textile technologies have been utilized to manufacture precision composite structures directly into their near-net shapes. One of the emerging technology involves 3D braiding of a fabric preform, followed by impregnating it with a binding material and consolidating the composite into the desired shape. From the standpoint of design and analysis, it is observed that a unique network of yarns is manufactured by the braiding process; and this network plays a dominant role in furnishing the properties of the composite. In fact, starting from the initial braiding setup to the performance of the composite, several connecting relations exist: the relations between the braiding setup and the preform shape, between the braiding steps and the yarn network topology, between the composite's global dimensions and the final yarn network, and between the yarn network and the composite properties. In short, there is a continuous relation between the functional performance of the composite and the ways by which it is braided, shaped and fabricated.

This paper considers a class of 3D braided composites of tubular cross-sections, and attempts to describe the interrelations in each step of their fabrication and characterization processes. The analytical effort begins with defining the key parameters for the braiding set-up, braiding steps and the resulting yarn network topology in the considered class of preforms. When an actual preform is braided with known yarn and consolidated with known matrix, the final yarn network in the composite is determined by composite's exterior dimensions in conjunction with the yarn topology in the preform before matrix consolidation. Finally, based on the actual yarn network in the composite, the thermomechanical properties are then predicted by a suitable micromechanics model.

Preforms braided by the 4-step 1x1 procedure are considered for purpose of definiteness in each level of the analysis. And, a 12K graphite yarn and an epoxy resin with known properties are used in the illustrative examples. Two tubes of differing braiding parameters but of the same inner radius

and the same tube wall thickness are analyzed. The results show that both the geometry of the yarn networks and the thermoelastic properties in the respective tubes are influenced by the initial braiding parameters. It is then further demonstrated that the interrelationships derived in each step of the analysis will provide the necessary basis for an optimization design loop, involving material selection, design of the beading setup pattern, actual braiding details, parameter selections of matrix consolidation, the expected yarn structure, and the final composite properties.

BRAIDING-YARN STRUCTURE-PROPERTY RELATIONS.

BRAIDING SETUP FOR TUBULAR PREFORMS.

A full description of the 4-step 1x1 braiding procedure has been detailed in [1]. Fig. 1 shows a schematic illustration of the braiding setup: the preform being braided is hung above the machine bed, on which yarn carriers are arranged in a pattern consisting of circumferential rows and radial columns. Let M be the number of yarn carriers in each circular row and N be the number of yarn carriers in each radial column; then the braiding setup is expressed as $[M \times N]$. The preform is braided through movements of the yarn carriers along the row and column tracks. There are 4 row-and-column movements in each cycle, during which yarn lines are first made to crisscross in space and then subject to a certain jamming (tightening of the yarns) action; a finite preform length is thus braided during one cycle, known as a pitch. The yarn structure so formed during each braiding cycle will repeat itself in successive cycles. Usually, a mandrel of fixed radius (say, R_1) is used in the braiding as shown in Fig. 1; this then adds a size parameter (R_1) to the initial braiding setup.

BRAIDING STEPS AND YARN TOPOLOGY

The yarn structure formed during each braiding cycle can be described topologically first (details contained in [2]). This is done by considering the yarn as a line tracing the yarn lines in a control space during the braiding cycle. At this point, the topology can be characterized by a set of free-parameters, whose values will ultimately be determined by several factors, including the size of the yarn used, the degree of yarn jamming, the conditions of matrix consolidation and the final dimensions of the preform. The following discusses some of the key elements in this regard.

Fig. 2 shows schematically the geometry of the yarn topology in the tubular preform. A global view of the preform interior is shown in 2a, where two families of curved plates (represented by the plate mid-planes) crisscross each other at the angle $2\alpha(r)$, r being the radial position of the crisscrossing point (α is the angle between the curved plate and the circle of radius r). At a smaller scale, the curved plate is formed by two layers of parallel yarn lines which crisscross at the angle of $2\gamma(r)$ as shown in 2b (γ is the angle between the yarn line and the braiding axis of the preform). The length scale defining the crisscrossing pattern in the plate is the braiding pitch h . Fig. 2c shows the yarn topology on the preform's inner surface, where crisscrossing yarn segments are formed (a similar formation is found on the preform's outer surface, not shown). The surface yarn pattern is characterized by the angle θ_{1s} on the inner surface, and by θ_{2s} on the outer surface. Generally, $\theta_{1s} \neq \theta_{2s}$. If the preform is braided with $[M \times N]$ and if the inner and outer radii of the preform are R_1 and R_2 , respectively, then from geometry:

$$\tan\theta_{1s} = 2\pi R_1/Mh \quad \tan\theta_{2s} = 2\pi R_2/Mh \quad (1)$$

In actual braiding situations, the braiding yarn is selected and yarn jamming during braiding is uniform; then a uniform yarn-to-yarn spacing, d , throughout the preform is assumed. The thickness of the curved plates (shown in Fig. 2b) is $2d$. Hence, d is a key parameter in determining the inter-relationship linking the braiding pitch h , the braiding setup parameters $[M \times N]$ and the inner and outer radii R_1 , R_2 . This inter-relation has been derived earlier in [3]:

$$2\pi(N/M)/\lambda = \sqrt{2} \left\{ \sqrt{[(R_2/R_1)^2 - 1/(2\lambda^2)]} - [(1/\lambda\sqrt{2})\sec^{-1}(\sqrt{2}\lambda R_2/R_1) - \sqrt{[1 - 1/(2\lambda^2)]}] \right\}$$

$$+ (1/\sqrt{2}\lambda)\sec^{-1}(\lambda\sqrt{2}) \quad (2)$$

where

$$\lambda = (2\pi R_1)/(Md\sqrt{2}) \quad (3)$$

Using the above, the yarn line angles $\alpha(r)$ and $\gamma(r)$ in the preform interior are determined as:

$$\sin\alpha = R_1/(\tau\lambda\sqrt{2}) \quad \tan\gamma = 2\sqrt{2} \tan\theta_{2S}/(\lambda' \sin 2\alpha) \quad (4)$$

where

$$\lambda' = (2\pi R_2)/(Md\sqrt{2}) \quad (5)$$

FINAL YARN STRUCTURE.

Given the tubular preform braided by [MxN] after matrix consolidation, the values of h , R_1 and R_2 are measured from the tube's exterior. Then, the yarn structure in the tube is totally characterized by the relations (1-5). In these relations, the yarn-to-yarn spacing d is related to the actual yarn used and the degree of yarn jamming during braiding. Thus, in general, h , R_1 and R_2 must be actually measured; they cannot be arbitrarily specified.

If, given the braiding yarn, the solid cross-section A_f of the yarn is known, the fiber volume content in the tube is given by:

$$V_f = (A_f M^2)/(4\pi^2 r^2 \tan\alpha \cos\gamma) \quad (6)$$

DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS.

In preform design, both R_1 and R_2 may be specified at the outset, followed by yarn selection, the braiding setup parameters [MxN] and yarn jamming during braiding, in anticipation of the desired yarn structure. The latter is, of course, characterized by the parameters h , $\alpha(r)$, $\gamma(r)$ and $V_f(r)$. Then, with the interrelations derived in (1-6), it is possible to perform the entire preform design in a closed-loop manner in order to achieve the desired yarn structure.

Furthermore, since the yarn structure plays a dominant role in furnishing the thermomechanical properties of the final composite, it is also possible to specify the composite properties in advance as a design element in the aforementioned loop. This can result in a complicated optimization situation in preform design.

MECHANICS MODELING AND PROPERTIES.

With the yarn structure in the composite tube fully described, the effective thermomechanical properties of the tube can be extracted by a suitable micromechanics model. Since the yarn structure in the tube consists of an interior core sandwiched between an inner and an outer surface layer, separate treatments of the core and the surface layers are necessary [2]. However, if the tube is braided with large [MxN], effects of the thin surface layers may be disregarded; characterization of the interior core alone will be sufficient.

THERMOELASTIC MODELING.

As shown in Fig. 2a, the interior yarn structure in the tube is first represented by two families of crisscrossing curved plates. At a smaller scale, each of the curved plates is composed of two layers of parallel yarns, see Fig. 2b. Thus, the curved plates can be modeled as a curved $[\pm\gamma]$ angle-ply laminate of thickness $2d$; and the $+\gamma$ or $-\gamma$ lamina can be modeled as an off-axis unidirectional (UD)

ply of thickness d .

Here, the UD ply will be treated as a linearly elastic, transversely isotropic material in its principal coordinates (L, T, z); the five elastic constants are determined according to the model by Chamis [5]:

$$E_L = V_f E_f + (1 - V_f) E_m \quad E_T (= E_z) = E_m / [1 - (1 - E_m / E_f) \sqrt{V_f}] \quad (7)$$

$$G_{LT} = G_m / [1 - (1 - G_m / G_f) \sqrt{V_f}] \quad (8)$$

$$v_{LT} = V_f v_f + (1 - V_f) v_m \quad v_{Tz} = [E_T / (2G_{LT}) - 1] \quad (9)$$

The thermal expansion coefficients of the UD ply are found via the model by Schapery [6]:

$$\beta_L = [\beta_f E_f V_f + \beta_m E_m (1 - V_f)] / [E_f V_f + E_m (1 - V_f)] \quad (10)$$

$$\beta_T = \beta_z = \beta_f V_f (1 + v_f) + \beta_m (1 - V_f) (1 + v_m) - \beta_L [v_f V_f + v_m (1 - V_f)] \quad (11)$$

These thermoelastic constants are subjected to a coordinate rotation about the z -axis locally through the angle $+\gamma$ or $-\gamma$, respectively, so that the angle-plyed $[\pm\gamma]$ plate can be modeled accordingly. This is done here by a volume-average procedure similar to that outlined by Pagano [7]. Specifically, the in-series model is used to derive the in-plane laminate properties by volume-averaging the associated lamina stiffness constants, and the out-of-plane properties by volume-averaging the associated lamina compliance constants. For brevity, however, the detailed expressions for the thermoelastic constants of the off-axis lamina and the $[\pm\gamma]$ laminate will be omitted here; details are found in [2].

Finally, let the coordinates (1,2,3) be used to describe the properties of the overall tube. Let axis-1 be in the tube's longitudinal direction, axis-2 in the circumferential direction and axis-3 in the radial direction. Since the 2 families of curved plates intersects the concentric circle of radius r with the angle $\alpha(r)$ and $-\alpha(r)$, respectively (Fig. 2a), the thermoelastic constants of each of the $[\pm\gamma]$ plates are first transformed to the global coordinates (1,2,3); then, the thermoelastic constants of the overall tube are found by volume-averaging the compliance. The overall tube is effectively orthotropic in the coordinates (1,2,3). Again, for brevity, the exact expressions for these properties are omitted here.

ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES.

Two tubular preforms that are to be braided using a 12K graphite yarn and to be consolidated with an epoxy resin will be considered as illustrative examples. The following properties are given at the material selection stage: the solid cross-sectional area of the yarn, $A_f = 0.477 \text{ mm}^2$; the elastic moduli of the fiber, $E_f = 234.4 \text{ GPa}$; the Poisson ratio of the fiber, $v_f = 0.22$; the thermal expansion coefficient of the fiber, $\beta_f = 0$; the elastic modulus of the matrix, $E_m = 34.5 \text{ GPa}$; the Poisson ratio, $v_m = 0.34$; and the thermal expansion Coefficient, $\beta_m = 70 \mu\epsilon/\text{C}$. In addition, the yarn-to-yarn spacing of the 12K graphite yarn under maximum yarn jamming condition is $d_{\min} = 0.6 \text{ mm}$.

Now, let a tubular preform be designed, braided and matrix-consolidated with the final inner radius $R_1 = 60 \text{ mm}$ and outer radius $R_2 = 100 \text{ mm}$. The initial design will be illustrated as follows:

Consistent with the yarn used, the required final tube dimensions and assuming uniform yarn jamming, the braiding pitch is selected as $h = 4 \text{ mm}$ and the yarn-to-yarn spacing is selected as $d = 0.7 \text{ mm}$. By satisfying equation (2), two possible braiding set-ups $[M \times N] = [380 \times 47]$ and $[M \times N] = [532 \times 35]$ are chosen. Between these two selected braiding setups, the resulting yarn structures in the respective preforms are significantly different. Fig. 3 shows the yarn structure parameters α, γ

and V_f as a function of radial position r for the two cases. In the former, the angle α is about 45° at the inner surface and it gradually decreases radially to about 25° at the outer surface; the angle γ increases from 35° to about 40° and the fiber volume fraction V_f decreases from 0.6 to about 0.5 in the same radial range. In contrast, the angle α in the latter case decreases sharply from 75° to about 40° radially. The radial behavior of the angle γ is rather erratic in that it decreases sharply from 50° to about 35° within the first-third of the tube thickness; it then remains at about 35° for the rest two-thirds of the tube thickness. The behavior of V_f is also quite erratic as can be seen from Fig. 3.

As expected, the differences in the yarn structures ultimately manifest themselves in the thermomechanical properties. Figs. 4 and 5 show the nine elastic constants and three thermal expansion coefficients in the tube's principal coordinates; these are plotted against the radial position r for the tube with [380x47] in Fig. 4, and for [532x35] in Fig. 5. The radial behaviors of these constants are seen to be relatively gradual in the former, while rather erratic in the latter, as well.

BRIEF DISCUSSIONS.

The above examples demonstrate that there is a range of possible braiding setups that can yield preforms with the prescribed overall dimensions. But the resulting yarn structure and, ultimately, the thermomechanical properties can differ widely. In practice, the thermomechanical properties may well be specified a priori, in addition to the specified yarn and the global tube dimensions. In that case, it is possible to conduct a selection for the M , N , h and d combination such that the resulting composite will meet all the preset requirements. The extent to which this can be done is provided by the analytical interrelations derived in the paper, as these interrelations form a closed design-and-analysis loop; the loop includes most if not all of the essential parameters that define the braiding setup, preform shaping, constituent materials properties and the geometric dimensions of the final composite. As can be expected, such a design procedure for 3D braided composites can be rather complex and situation-specific; this subject is outside the scope of the present paper, however.

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Fig. 1. Schematics of Braiding Setup for Tubular Preforms

Fig. 2. Yarn Topology in Tubular Preform: (a) the Interior Structure of Crisscrossing Plates; (b) Yarn Formation of the Curved Plate; (c) Yarn Formation on Inner Surface.

Fig. 3. Comparison of Topological Parameters in [380x47] and [532x35] Preforms

Fig. 4. Radial Variation of Properties in [380x47] Preform

Fig. 5. Radial Variation of Properties in [532x35] Preform